

The Effect of Flow Restriction Training on Knee Osteoarthritis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Abstract

Background: Although different studies have shown association of blood flow restriction (BFR) with exercise positive effects including muscle's strength gain and hypertrophy, activity and performance, no meta-analysis has evaluated the BFR effects in cases with knee osteoarthritis. Therefore, in this meta-analysis, we aimed to assess the effect of flow restriction training on treatment of knee osteoarthritis.

Methods: The Scopus, Google Scholar, EBSCO, PEDro, Web of Science, Embase, and Medline were assessed from inception until June 2021. This meta-analysis was performed according to the PRISMA guidelines using the following keywords: Therapeutic Occlusion, Resistance Training, and Knee Osteoarthritis, blood flow restriction and Kaatsu training. The quality of the included studies were assessed using the PEDro scale. Statistical analysis was carried out using Comprehensive Meta-Analysis software (CMA, version 3).

Results: Five studies were included in this meta-analysis with moderate to low risk bias. Our findings, revealed no difference between BFR and HLT with respect to knee strength (SMD =-0.00, 95% CI, -0.55 to 0.55, P =0.99), function (SMD =-0.22, 95% CI, -0.47 to 0.02, P =0.08), pain and volume. However, when compared BFR and LLT, the descriptive analysis showed significant findings in favor BFR to muscle strength and volume (MD =1.66, 95% CI, 0.93 to 2.38, P <0.00001), but not in pain or function.

Conclusion: BFR can be used as an intervention in the treatment of osteoarthritis due to effects in strength and volume with low mechanical stress. However, its usage must be safe and effective, since they can reduce the stimuli made by BFR.

Keywords: Kaatsu training, rehabilitation, resistance training, osteoarthritis, Treatment.

Introduction

Knee osteoarthritis is a joint disease with high prevalence, known by the existence of pain that can involve the leg or thigh, proposing cartilage damage and radiological changes of the knee (1, 2). Patients with osteoarthritis have also nocturnal pain, stiffness, muscle weakness, edema and loss of joint mobility, resulting in impairment of the functionality, emotional and social state of these cases (3, 4). Furthermore, patients with osteoarthritis are more susceptible to falls and fractures, due to the impairment of balance and proprioception. One of the aims of physiotherapeutic treatment in knee osteoarthritis cases is the exercise's functional gain. Results reported in previous studies since 2002 have shown that exercises for subjects with knee osteoarthritis is effective in amelioration of the symptoms, reducing pain and increasing muscle strength. In order to increase strength, The American College of Sports Medicine recommended 60–70% of a maximum repetition -1RM so that appropriate muscle fiber type II recruitment occurs (4, 5). This will not be obtained in weights below 60% of 1RM. Knee osteoarthritis cases undergoing 60–80% of 1RM high intensity strength training have shown discomfort and pain when training it, limiting and delaying treatment process. In contrast to high intensity strength training, there is novel model training at gaining strength with low intensity 20–50% of 1RM, correlated with blood flow restriction (BFR) (6-8). Recent studies have shown that low intensity aerobic training in combination with BFR can improve muscular size, strength and hypertrophy on the elderly and may be an intervention to reduce strength and muscle mass loss process during immobilization (7, 9). The BFR, also characterized by occlusion vascular training, constitutes of using a cuff that decrease the exercised limbs' blood flow, which in addition to the muscles' blood supply improve venous return. During BFR strength training, a cuff is used to the upper third of the inferior or superior limbs, then pressure is provided in the cuff, according to the tolerance of each patient. The BFR training leads to metabolic substances increased concentration, inducing various cellular and hormonal alterations which correlated with muscle hypoxia, make greater muscle fiber recruitment (10, 11). Although individual studies have shown BFR correlated with exercise positive effects, such as muscle's strength gain and hypertrophy, function and performance, no meta-analysis has assessed the BFR roles in the treatment of patients with knee osteoarthritis. Therefore, the aim of this meta-analysis is to investigate the effect of flow restriction training on knee osteoarthritis.

Methods

This meta-analysis included studies evaluating the BFR training effects on knees' osteoarthritis diagnosed cases symptoms systematic review, as well as those application results. Systematic review is known as the best method to provide the entire existing data on a particular subject, thus becoming extremely significant in health investigations. The process of identifying for and screening papers met all the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-analysis guidelines (PRISMA) recommended steps. A literature review was performed without restrictions on the language of publication, from the earliest papers up to July 2021 in electronic databases including Medline, Scopus, Google Scholar, The Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials – CENTRAL, Physiotherapy Evidence Database (PEDro), and EBSCO. The main keywords were used in English language included

Osteoarthritis, Therapeutic Occlusion, Resistance Training, and Pain. More keywords were used to increase search results: blood flow restriction and Kaatsu training; for each concept, keywords were combined with the 'AND' operator. This method of search was used by independent authors (SHSH and OB). Title and abstracts of the papers resulting from the search were first assessed, according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. If the title and abstract assessment eligibility was not clear, full text was received and evaluated and any eligibility of a particular paper disagreement was consensually solved. Inclusion criteria for the review were papers that included investigations with humans having randomized controlled trial as their methodology. Those papers were about using the BFR in knee osteoarthritis as a form of treatment. Systematic review studies and meta-analysis, integrative review, case reports, case series, observational studies, texts that did not have the aim of the review or that were duplicated in the search databases were excluded. Trials involving osteoarthritis diagnosed cases were included, but studies were excluded if the patients had other knee pathology, such as patellofemoral syndrome, or had had knee surgical intervention. Two independent authors extracted variables based in main outcomes, which were three: the first outcome included muscles' strength and volume, knee's function and during and after exercise pain/discomfort effects. As for the second outcomes the following were extracted: application and prescription of training. One reviewer performed data collection and analysis which was assessed by an independent statistician. To describe the knee osteoarthritis BFR intervention effect a meta-analysis using Comprehensive Meta-Analysis software (version 3) was performed. Meta-analysis was only carried out for those investigations that compared BFR exercise to HLT or LLT. Continuous outcomes' meta-analysis was performed using means and standard deviations (SDs) from each of the eligible studies. When data were presented in different outcome measures they were shown by standardized mean difference (SMD) and as mean difference (MD) if the investigation used the same outcome measure. Pooled data were analyzed with a random or fixed effect model based on the results of heterogeneity between studies assessed using the I^2 statistic, with thresholds set as $I^2 > 50\%$ (high). When a variable assessed had different measurements, all were considered and included in order to increase accuracy and thus generalization of our findings. Significance level was considered as a $P < 0.05$. To analyze the methodological quality of the studies included in this meta-analysis, The Physiotherapy Evidence Database rating scale was used, as well as evaluating the statistical description, and whether the investigation had minimal statistical data so that findings can be interpretable.

Results

Study Selection and Methodological Quality

A total of 684 papers in the databases were assessed. After the initial evaluation, only 20 papers were applied as to eligibility. Subsequently, duplicated papers and reviews were excluded, followed by reading and full analysis of the remaining investigations. Ultimately, five investigations fulfilled the criteria and were included in the meta-analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart of the literature search and selection of studies that reported effect of flow restriction training on knee osteoarthritis.

Of the five papers included in this meta-analysis, all had good (score ≥ 6 points) methodological quality. All papers revealed failed to blind the study cases and physicians and two investigations couldn't conceal group allocation. In detection bias, all investigations reported using blinded investigators for the outcome evaluations. All included investigations reported compliance between 70% and 100% and two papers stated dropouts $>15\%$. About subjects total exercise sessions completed specific percentage was higher than 80% in four investigations, only one didn't report subjects' completed number of sessions. Only two of the investigations included showed the intention-to-treat principle when performing their analyses.

Study Characteristics and BFR Training Interventions

Two papers were performed in Brazil and three in the United States. All of the papers were published between 2015 and 2019. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the included papers. In these investigations, 190 subjects were analyzed and their mean age was 59.89 ± 7.47 years, predominantly women. BFR was applied in combination with low load (20–30% 1RM) resistance training in all investigations and comparing with low load without BFR20 or only high load (60–80% 1RM). The equipment used to apply the BFR has been stated in only three investigations. In investigations that reported the cuff size, a variation between 6 and 18 cm in width was observed. The occlusive pressure in the investigations ranged from 100 to 200 mmg. Only one investigation selected a pressure based on the total occlusive pressure of the limbs or systolic blood pressure. The other investigators changed the cuff pressure according to the sessions, another applied a pre-determined pressure for all cases and a formula to find the pressure to be used. Duration of the BFR exercise intervention ranged from 4 to 12 weeks, with a frequency of two to three training times per week.

Table 1. Characteristics of the included studies.

Studies	Number of Patients	Age	BMI	Duration of Exercise	Size of Cuff	Exercise Intensity of BFR	Exercise Intensity of Control
Segal et al. (12)	40	55.4	30.4	4 Weeks	6 cm	30% De I RM	30% De I RM
Segal et al. (13)	41	57.3	30.9	4 Weeks	6 cm	30% De I RM	30% De I RM
Bryk et al. (14)	34	61.4	29.8	6 Weeks	NR	30% De I RM	70% De I RM
Ferraz et al. (7)	48	60.1	30.1	12 Weeks	18 cm	20% De I RM+30% De I RM	80% De I RM+30% De I RM
Harper et al. (15)	27	68.2	30.6	12 Weeks	NR	20% De I RM	60% De I RM

Outcome Measures

The outcome of knee function variables were performed through timed up and go test, timed position test, stair climb power, WOMAC, lequesne, late life function and disability instrument,

short physical performance battery and walking speed. The WOMAC Pain Sub-scale, KOOS pain and numeric pain rating scale were applied to rate pain variable. Bilateral leg press isotonic, isokinetic knee extensor, scaled leg press 1RM, scaled 40% 1RM leg press power, isometric voluntary contraction, leg press 1RM test, and knee extension 1RM test evaluated the muscle strength. Finally, muscle size was investigated by evaluating muscle CSA, muscle volume.

Meta-analysis

BFR ×High Load Training (HLT). Three investigations had data extracted for meta-analysis comparing knee osteoarthritis cases BFR with HLT. Meta-analyses were performed for two outcomes: knee muscle strength (Figure 2) and knee function (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Meta-analysis of comparison of muscle strength between BFR and high load groups.

Figure 3. Meta-analysis of comparison of knee function between BFR and high load groups.

In the knee muscle strength based in three studies there wasn't any difference effect between BFR and HLT group (SMD =-0.00, 95% CI, -0.55 to 0.55, P =0.99). As for knee function, three papers evaluated this outcome with difference ways and revealed increase in knee function favors to HLT (SMD =-0.22, 95% CI, -0.47 to 0.02, P =0.08). Only one paper showed muscle volume variable comparing BFR to HLT, and it revealed small effect in favor to HLT, but not significant (MD =-0.29, 95% CI, -0.98 to 0.41, P =0.42). The data extracted from the three studies did not yielded a meta-analysis of knee muscle strength to be performed, due to the lack of homogeneity ($I^2 > 90%$). Although muscle strength meta-analysis between BFR and LLT was not possible, the descriptive analysis revealed that five out of seven assessments had a significant effect in favor of the BFR group. Only one paper assessed muscle volume outcome measure comparing BFR to LLT, and it revealed effect in favors to BFR (MD =1.66, 95% CI, 0.93 to 2.38, P<0.00001). There wasn't effect difference between BFR and LLT group (MD =-0.167, 95% CI, -0.60 to 0.27, P=0.45), in two studies based in knee pain, described in Figure 4. For knee function two papers evaluated this outcome in different ways, but the increase in knee function was similar between BFR and LLT, Figure 5 (SMD =-0.006, 95% CI, -0.37 to 0.36, P=0.97).

Figure 4. Meta-analysis of comparison of knee pain between BFR and low load groups.

Figure 5. Meta-analysis of comparison of knee function between BFR and low load groups.

Discussion

There is a growing number of studies using BFR as a clinical musculoskeletal interventional method; however, the efficacy of this novel exercise method in the treatment of knee osteoarthritis has not yet been assessed. Therefore, this meta-analysis has performed to investigate its roles in clinical amelioration and comparing its findings with HLT and LLT, but assessed the different methods about BFR usage in these subjects. Findings revealed that BFR training makes similar responses to HLT in muscular strength, volume, knee pain and function in cases with knee osteoarthritis. When it's compared with LLT alone, the BFR training showed more effective results in muscle volume and strength. Therefore, the BFR training can be used as a clinical amelioration method in knee osteoarthritis for cases who can't do HLT (16, 17). The BFR muscle strength and volume increase was found in all exercise methods, regardless of the duration of the independent intervention. Recent investigations have reported similar effects in knee extensor muscle strengthening trainings with results between 8% and 13%. This was seen due to the neuromuscular adaptations made by the BFR during training, which makes a reduction in oxygen in the muscle, leading to a hypoxic environment, making greater recruitment of type II fibers, levels of IL-6 and growing hormone. Therefore, BFR training during the period of 4–12 weeks thought to lead to a significant increase in strength similar to HLT exercise and higher effect to LLT in a case with knee osteoarthritis. However, LLT revealed lower gains in muscle volume than BFR and HLT. Recent studies showed that thigh muscle mass has been associated with muscle strength, activity and symptomatic progressions in females with knee osteoarthritis. Therefore, during the amelioration period of these cases, aim should not be only on achievement of strength, but also on increasing muscle mass (17, 18). Our meta-analysis came up with the same results that other meta-analysis which seen that BFR was equally effective in increasing muscle mass in comparison with HL-RT in older cases. However, even though LLT thought to be an appropriate choice to strength gains, activity and to reduce pain in patients with knee osteoarthritis, it doesn't have any significant effect in muscle mass. This is approved by investigations that revealed BFR exercise can provide a more effective results compared to LLT and more tolerable approach to HLT during knee osteoarthritis treatment. During treatment application of the knee osteoarthritis cases, the progression of the load is crucial so that muscular adaptations provided by the training continue. However, no investigations performed progression of load during the training protocol, which can decrease the results of training provided in a knee osteoarthritis case. Literature also recommended that the load volume affects muscle adaptations, but there is no consensus whether muscle adaptations improved by BFR are caused by metabolic stress caused by muscle hypoxia or exercise volumes similar to HLT (18-20). A recent study comparing BFR exercise and LLT over 6 weeks, revealed the volume of the exercise to be 33% lower and findings favorable to BFR group, but without any statistically significant difference. It was shown that all osteoarthritis treatments are due to neural activation and increased quadriceps strength, since these cases have reduced this musculature strength due to arthrogenic muscle

inhibition. Neural inhibition process reduces quadriceps activation as much as possible and may lead to functional atrophy or deficit. The quadriceps muscle weakness is correlated with pain in lifting, sitting and walking functions, it results in lower functional capacity and higher elderly falls likelihood. In this meta-analysis, it was seen that the investigations included assess cases older adults (>50 years), mostly postmenopausal patients and cases whose body mass was above 25 kg/m² (20). These features are correlated with higher joint stress that take a cycle of pain, loss of strength and knee activity due to impaired cartilage and changing joint mechanics; leading to high prevalence in the elderly. However, for cases with these physical and functional features, HLT training recommendation can be very challenging or contraindicated due to the joint degeneration caused by osteoarthritis. Bryk et al. (14) revealed that BFR group had lower levels of joint pain during training when compared to cases who received HLT.

This meta-analysis heterogeneity revealed in some outcomes can be clarified by the diversity in the BFR application and used exercise methods. Investigations on types of BFR usages revealed that cuff size affects technique provided metabolic reactions. A recent investigation shows that the 13/12 cm cuff attenuates muscle growth, makes discomfort during training and allows less safety, and it shows the narrow cuff for better training findings. Other study with 38 investigation showed that BRF application of wide cuffs make higher levels of discomfort than narrow cuffs (19, 21). The greater cuffs discomfort still caused lower adherence to training and rehabilitation interventions in the investigations. In this meta-analysis, only three studies showed cuff width, whereas cuffs size was 6 cm and 18 cm, but none of these trials assessed discomfort during training, and the only investigator to evaluate this aspect did not stated cuff size used. Lack of description in cuff size in some investigations led to not being possible to find cuffs effect in this population's amelioration. However, based on the findings of previous studies, the use of narrow cuff seems to be more effective and safe. Loenneke et al. (22) add those investigators who ignore cuff size may not only decrease treatment effectiveness, but may make application a risk to case safety and health. Another aspect to be considered for the BFR use in clinical environment could be the application of individualized ideal pressure aiming at higher efficacy and safety. In the investigations included, only two investigators seemed to find pressure of each case, but in the other studies the same pressure strategy was used for all cases. This may be one of the variables that especially clarify findings inconsistencies from outcomes evaluated in the investigations included. Harper et al. (15) applied cuff pressure based on the equation [pressure mm Hg =0.5 (systolic blood pressure) +2(thigh circumference) +5], however, the application of these formula does not show sufficient scientific evidence for their use. Ferraz et al. (7) applied a pressure value calculation is needed to cause artery total occlusion, using BFR 70% of the pressure, but literature evidence suggests not using high percentages. Some studies showed that 40–50% (low occlusion pressure) of the pressure needed to cause total occlusion of the artery, correlated with low intensity training findings equal in muscle strength gain and mass compared with high percent of occlusion (>60%) (23, 24). The difference between high and low occlusion percentage is that low occlusion pressure makes less discomfort during training. In this meta-analysis, some investigators ignored patient's cuff individual features. Bryk et al. (14)

applied standard cuff pressure for all cases (200 mmHg), where a doppler was applied only to approve that there was no total vascular occlusion, despite stating positive findings, this usage form is not suggested. Two studies using initial pressures 100–120 mmHg, increasing 20 mmHg with each series, with 10 seconds of deflation, method used until reaching the final pressure, which ranged from 160 to 200 mmHg. Another variable little explained and addressed in the investigations is the cuff deflation roles during rest period carried out by Segal et al. (12, 13). In this regard, few studies have investigated training chronic roles with or without BFR during rest, and they revealed that there was no difference between the two BFR usage types. Previous studies showed the need for pressure's use personalized prescription to receive appropriate blood flow restriction, considering limb circumference for the best performance during exercise (25, 26). The thigh circumference as an indicating predictor of BFR pressure, with larger limbs needing higher levels of pressure to obtain the same level of occlusion as smaller limbs. It can be clarified because male patients commonly have greater thigh circumference than female patients. It's possible to see that investigations using the same training strategy and BFRg usage in male and female patients, showed different findings. Taken together, this meta-analysis showed BFR has been applied as an amelioration interventional method for patients with knee osteoarthritis. Our results suggested BFR in the osteoarthritis treatment can be positive for strength gain, muscle hypertrophy, decreasing pain and discomfort in performing training or daily life functions, as described in papers. Furthermore, findings reveal that BFR has similar HLT roles and higher than LLT in muscle strength and volume. Therefore, BFR can make LLT effects in patients with knee osteoarthritis and less mechanical stress than HLT during training (16, 27). However, this meta-analysis shows aspects of this population's BFR usage, where it was seen that there was no usage individualization in most trials, which has an effect on most of the findings reported. In this regard, any physician who selects the use of BFR training must take into account the aspects described, not only aiming at technique's higher efficiency but also patient's safety and health. The current meta-analysis has some restrictions due to the low number of papers included and the finding of literature, but it is possible to see positive roles of BFR in cases with knee osteoarthritis. The lack of homogeneity of the investigations included made some analyses impossible, and one can believe that this was seen due to training protocol different interventions, BFR usage and different methods of assessing the same outcome. The third restriction is that there was no long duration of follow-up of the investigations found seeking to approve the roles of BFR, and to compare it with other treatments. The fourth restriction and non-blinding of the cases in all investigations included, in addition to the impossibility of masking the physician (27, 28). Finally, based on our findings we recommend the use of BRF exercise in cases with knee osteoarthritis during the amelioration period. It is also crucial that the physician consider the best method to use BFR in their clinic, since when used incorrectly it may not lead to good results. It is worth assessing that for cases with acute pain and loss of activity, the application of this method in amelioration becomes viable and may be more effective than LLT and HLT. We recommend that future investigations to individualize the usage

of BFR, perform load progression and a long term follow-up of these cases in addition to the higher levels of methodological quality of the investigations with sample blinding.

Conclusion

There are evidences showing that BFR seems to be effective in reducing manifestations and pain in patients with knee osteoarthritis, increasing knee function, muscle volume and strength. The BFR in cases with knee osteoarthritis can be more effective than LLT and even HLT when subject does not tolerate high pressures due lower stress mechanical. The results suggest those different types of application must take into account the individual features of cases and cuffs as they are crucial for the safety and efficacy of BFR.

Declarations

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Author Contribution

Shahram Shokraneh: Study design, review of literature, writing draft of study.

Amin Basharkhah: Study design, review of literature, writing draft of study.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

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